

LONG-RUN IMPACT OF PUBLIC SECTOR INVESTMENT IN EDUCATION AND HEALTH ON NIGERIA'S ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: Nigeria's economic performance is intricately linked to its investments in the public sector, particularly education and health. It is therefore against this backdrop that this study examined the long-run impact of public sector investment in education and health on Nigeria's economic performance between 1986 and 2023, with real GDP (LNRGDP) as the dependent variable, while public investment in education (LNPSIE), public investment in health (LNPSIH), literacy rate (LITR), and life expectancy (LEXP) served as the explanatory variables. The analysis employed the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) estimation technique after confirming stationarity of the variables at first difference and the presence of cointegration among the variables. Data for the study were culled from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, the World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI), and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The descriptive statistics revealed that all variables were normally distributed, with life expectancy and literacy rate showing relative stability compared to public investment measures. The correlation results indicated strong positive associations between human capital variables and economic growth. The unit root and Johansen cointegration tests confirmed long-run relationships among the variables. The FMOLS results showed that public investment in education exerted a negative and statistically insignificant impact on economic growth, suggesting inefficiencies in the Nigerian education system. Conversely, public investment in health had a positive and significant effect on growth, while literacy rate displayed

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a positive but weakly significant effect. Life expectancy emerged as the most influential factor, exhibiting a strong and highly significant positive impact on economic growth. The study concluded that human capital development significantly influences Nigeria's economic growth and thus recommend that government should prioritize efficient education spending, scale up healthcare investment, promote literacy and skills development, enhance life expectancy through health and social policies, and strengthen institutional frameworks to ensure human capital investments translate into sustainable economic growth.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Nigeria's economic performance over the last two decades has been shaped not only by commodity shocks and macroeconomic policy but also by the country's persistent human-capital shortfalls. Improvements in population health and educational attainment raise labour productivity, increase labour force participation, and encourage technological adoption - channels through which public investments in health and education translate into higher long-run output per capita. International frameworks, including the World Bank's Human Capital Index, explicitly link gains in health and education to future productivity and earnings, highlighting how shortfalls in schooling quality and health reduce lifetime productivity and GDP potential (World Bank, 2020).

Public sector investment in health and education is widely recognized as a critical driver of human capital development, which in

turn fosters long-term economic growth in developing economies like Nigeria. These investments enhance workforce productivity, innovation, and overall societal well-being, aligning with Keynesian economic theory that emphasizes government spending to stimulate aggregate demand and long-run output (Christopher, Akpan and Ologunla, 2025; Okerekeoti, 2022). In Nigeria, where economic performance is often measured by metrics such as GDP per capita and sustainable development indicators, public expenditures in these sectors aim to address persistent challenges like poverty, inequality, and low human development indices (Akujuobi and Tony-Okolo, 2023; Abiodun and Okon, 2023). Despite Nigeria's status as Africa's largest economy, inadequate funding - often below international benchmarks such as UNESCO's 26% of budget for education - has historically limited the effectiveness of these investments, leading to inefficiencies, crowding-out effects on

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private sector involvement, and delayed economic benefits.

Historically, Nigeria's economic performance has been volatile, influenced by oil dependency, inflation, and external shocks, with public health and education spending averaging around 3-7% of the national budget over the past decades. This underinvestment has contributed to suboptimal outcomes, such as high unemployment rates among the youth and health crises that reduce labour productivity. Recent empirical studies underscore the need for sustained, efficient public investments to achieve long-run positive impacts on economic growth and sustainable development (World Bank, 2023; World Health Organization, 2023; UNESCO, 2024).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite Nigeria's abundant natural resources and large labour force, the country's economic performance has remained volatile and below potential, with persistent challenges of low productivity, widespread poverty, and high inequality. While theory and evidence suggest that public investment in human capital - particularly in education and health - should enhance long-run growth by improving skills, literacy, and life expectancy, Nigeria's experience reveals a paradox. On one hand, government expenditure on education and health has increased over the years, often through budgetary allocations and donor-supported initiatives; on the other hand, human

development outcomes such as literacy rates and life expectancy remain among the lowest globally. According to recent World Bank and WHO reports, Nigeria's literacy rate is still below the sub-Saharan African average, while life expectancy at birth lags far behind that of emerging economies, reflecting weak health and educational systems.

This disconnect raises fundamental concerns about the effectiveness and productivity of public sector investment in human capital. If rising expenditure is not translating into measurable improvements in literacy and life expectancy, or into stronger economic growth, then either resources are being misallocated, inefficiencies are undermining outcomes, or complementary factors such as governance and infrastructure are missing. Previous empirical studies in Nigeria provide mixed results: some report a positive and significant long-run effect of education and health expenditure on real GDP, while others find weak or insignificant linkages once human capital indicators and structural factors are introduced.

Given these contradictions, it is unclear whether public expenditure on education and health, alongside key human capital indicators like literacy rate and life expectancy, exerts a strong and sustainable influence on Nigeria's real GDP in the long run. This uncertainty creates a policy dilemma, as government continues to commit scarce fiscal resources toward education and health in the hope of boosting long-term

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growth. Hence, the critical problem is the lack of empirical clarity on whether such investments genuinely enhance Nigeria's economic performance, or whether structural inefficiencies and poor outcomes in literacy and life expectancy dilute their growth impact. This study seeks to rigorously examine the long-run impact of public expenditure on education and health, literacy rate, and life expectancy on Nigeria's economic performance (proxied by real GDP), thereby providing evidence-based guidance for policy formulation.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the long-run impact of public sector investment in health and education on Nigeria's economic performance. The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the long-run effect of public expenditure on education on Nigeria's real GDP.
2. Evaluate the long-run effect of public expenditure on health on Nigeria's real GDP.
3. Investigate the impact of literacy rate on Nigeria's real GDP.
4. Examine the impact of life expectancy on Nigeria's real GDP.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the long-run effect of public expenditure on education on Nigeria's real GDP?
2. To what extent does public expenditure on health influence Nigeria's real GDP in the long run?

3. How does literacy rate affect Nigeria's real GDP?

4. What role does life expectancy play in explaining Nigeria's real GDP?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

For empirical testing, the hypotheses are in their null forms (H_0):

1. H_{01} : Public expenditure on education has no significant long-run effect on Nigeria's real GDP.
2. H_{02} : Public expenditure on health has no significant long-run effect on Nigeria's real GDP.
3. H_{03} : Literacy rate has no significant effect on Nigeria's real GDP.
4. H_{04} : Life expectancy has no significant effect on Nigeria's real GDP.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is important because it provides fresh empirical evidence on how public expenditure on education and health, together with literacy rate and life expectancy, affect Nigeria's long-run economic performance. Unlike previous works that focus mainly on government spending, this research combines fiscal allocations with outcome-based human capital indicators, thereby offering a more comprehensive understanding of how resources and actual improvements in human development translate into economic growth. The findings will help policymakers evaluate whether current investments in education and health are yielding the desired macroeconomic

benefits and guide more efficient budget allocation in the face of fiscal constraints. In addition, the study has practical value for development partners such as the World Bank, WHO, and UNESCO, who support Nigeria's human capital programmes. By updating the analysis with recent data and applying robust econometric methods, the research strengthens the academic literature on human capital and growth while serving as a reference for scholars and students. Overall, the results will inform evidence-based policy decisions that can enhance Nigeria's human capital development and ensure that public sector investments contribute effectively to long-term economic growth.

1.7 Scope of the Study

This study focuses on examining the long-run impact of public sector investment in health and education on Nigeria's economic performance, using real gross domestic product (RGDP) as the dependent variable. The explanatory variables include public expenditure on education, public expenditure on health, literacy rate, and life expectancy, which jointly capture both fiscal commitment to human capital development and the actual outcomes of such investments. The study covers the period 1981 to 2024, a timeframe chosen to provide a long-run perspective and to capture structural reforms, policy changes, and economic shocks that have shaped Nigeria's growth trajectory. Secondary data will be sourced from reliable

publications such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI), and World Health Organization (WHO) databases. The analysis will employ appropriate econometric techniques to test both short-run and long-run relationships, while focusing on Nigeria as a single-country case study.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.2.1 Public Sector Investment

Public sector investment refers to the expenditure by governments on creating long-term assets that benefit society and support economic growth. This includes spending on physical infrastructure like roads, bridges, and buildings, as well as investments in education and healthcare (Zaranko, 2024). Public investment is crucial for providing public goods and services that the private sector may not efficiently supply, such as defense and public utilities. It is typically measured as a percentage of national income and can influence economic development by enhancing productivity and facilitating private sector activity (Lee, 2023). As government spending, public sector investment focus on the collective or individual needs and wants of public goods and public services, such as pension, healthcare, security, education subsidies, emergency services, infrastructure, etc (Akrani, 2012). According to Ajie, Ewubare and Akekere (2014), public sector

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investment refers to the resources government allocates to achieve its strategic goal to satisfy the needs of its members. Government areas of investment include health care, education, Social Security benefits, infrastructure, and defense activities. Public investment in economic growth is rooted in Keynesian economics, which advocates for government intervention to stimulate aggregate demand and capital accumulation (Onifade, Cevik and Erdogan, 2020). Until the 19th century, public investment was limited due to laissez faire philosophies, observed Berkeley, (2022). In the 20th century, John Maynard Keynes (1936) argued that the role of public investment was pivotal in determining levels of income and distribution in the economy. Public investment plays an important role in the economy as it establishes fiscal policy and provides public goods and services for households and firms. According to Barro and Grilli (1994), in national income accounting, the acquisition by governments of goods and services for current use, to directly satisfy the individual or collective needs of the community, is classed as government final consumption expenditure. Government acquisition of goods and services intended to create future benefits, such as infrastructure investment or research spending, is classed as government investment (government gross capital formation). These two types of government spending, on final consumption and on gross capital formation,

together constitute one of the major components of gross domestic product.

2.1.2 Public Sector Investment in Education

Education is globally recognized as a strategic driver of economic transformation, providing the human capital and technological know-how necessary for development. In Nigeria, studies show that education significantly contributes to GDP growth, though the sector remains underfunded, particularly at basic and secondary levels. Underfunding has led to poor infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and declining education quality, which undermine economic progress (Adetula, Adesina, Owolabi and Ojeka, 2024; Bosco, Omekwe, Omiekuma and Obayori, 2019). Education fosters skills development, innovation, and productivity, which are critical for sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, and ICT. Nigeria's budgetary allocations to education have been falling below UNESCO's recommended 26% for developing nations, hindering potential growth. While short-term effects may be muted, sustained investment in education (e.g., tertiary-level research) can spur industrial transformation and reduce reliance on foreign aid (Egbule, Okonye and Mokuwunyei, 2022). Despite its potential, Nigeria's education system faces systemic challenges including underfunding and delays in fund disbursement exacerbating infrastructural deficits and teacher strikes. Geometric increases in student enrolment are

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not matched by proportional infrastructure development. Inadequate funding drives skilled professionals abroad, depriving the economy of critical expertise (Adetula, Adesina, Owolabi and Ojeka, 2024).

2.1.3 Public Sector Investment in Health

Public investment in health as an indicator is defined as the level of general government expenditure on health (GGHE) expressed as a percentage of total government expenditure. It shows the weight of public spending on health within the total value of public sector operations. This indicator includes not just the resources channelled through government budgets, but also the expenditures channelled through government entities for health by parastatals, extra-budgetary entities and, notably, compulsory health insurance. The indicator refers to resources collected and pooled by public agencies, including all revenue modalities (WHO, 2019). According to OECD (2022), global health expenditure per capita in 2021 was estimated to be around 1,100–\$1,260.36 USD, with significant variations between high-income and low-income countries. High-income countries often spend several thousand dollars per capita annually on health, while low-income countries may spend less than \$100 per capita. Nigeria's health sector suffers from chronic underfunding and inefficiencies. Public health expenditure is only 5.03% of GDP in 2023 (below the WHO-recommended 15%), with over 70% of

healthcare costs paid out-of-pocket by households (World Bank, 2024). Limited facilities (e.g., only 7 cancer radiotherapy centres for 200M people) and brain drain of medical professionals exacerbate service gaps (Oboko, 2025). Health investments indirectly boost agriculture and manufacturing by improving workforce capacity. For example, malnutrition reduction programs can elevate agricultural productivity (Lancet Commission 2022; Awoyemi, Makanju Mpapalika and Ekpeyo, 2023).

2.1.4 Literacy Rate

The literacy rate is the percentage of people in a given population who can read and write with understanding in at least one language. It is a key indicator of educational attainment and socioeconomic development in a country. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), literacy is defined as:

“The ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts”.

UNESCO further specifies that a literate person is someone who can perform basic reading and writing tasks necessary for daily life and work. Nigeria's adult literacy rate (ages 15 and above) for the period of study showed fluctuations with an overall gradual improvement but remained relatively low compared to global averages. The World Bank data and other sources confirm a

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steady upward trend with some variability, with literacy rates reaching around 63-69% in recent years (World Bank, 2023; Statista, 2023). Key challenges affecting literacy include regional disparities (notably lower rates in northern Nigeria), poverty, insecurity, and cultural factors such as child marriage. The government has prioritized literacy improvement through policies and partnerships, aiming also to boost digital literacy by 2030 (Nielsen, 2021). In summary, Nigeria's adult literacy rate has improved from roughly 54-55% in the early 1990s to about 62-69% by the early 2020s but still faces significant challenges in achieving universal literacy.

2.1.5 Life Expectancy

Human life expectancy is a statistical measure of the estimate of the average remaining years of life at a given age. The most commonly used measure is life expectancy at birth (LEB, or in demographic notation e_0 , where e_x denotes the average life remaining at age x). This can be defined in two ways. According to Shyrock and Siegel (1973), cohort LEB is the mean length of life of a birth cohort (in this case, all individuals born in a given year) and can be computed only for cohorts born so long ago that all their members have died. Period LEB is the mean length of life of a hypothetical cohort assumed to be exposed, from birth through death, to the mortality rates observed at a given year. National LEB figures reported by national agencies and international organizations for

human populations are estimates of period LEB (Shyrock and Siegel, 1973; Office of National Statistics, 2020; Our World in Data, 2020). Nigeria's life expectancy ranks 167th globally (WHO, 2020), below the African average (65 years) and far behind high-income nations (e.g., Japan: 84.9 years), WHO (2023). According to WHO (2023), communicable diseases (malaria, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis) account for significant mortality, while mortality associated to non-communicable diseases (hypertension, diabetes) and injuries (road accidents) are rising. Socioeconomic factors such as multidimensional poverty limits access to nutrition and sanitation. Air pollution and unsafe water also contribute to mortality in Nigeria, leading to low life expectancy.

2.1.6 Linkage between public investment in education, public investment in health, literacy rate, life expectancy and economic growth

Public expenditure on education raises schooling access, human capital formation and skill acquisition, which increases labour productivity, facilitates technology adoption, and improves total factor productivity — all of which raise long-run RGDP per capita. Public health spending improves population health (fewer sick days, higher physical and cognitive capacity), increases effective labour supply and labour productivity, and raises returns to education by improving learning outcomes. Literacy rate is a direct outcome measure of

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education quality and human capital accumulation; higher literacy raises worker adaptability and productivity. Life expectancy reflects cumulative health conditions and affects investment decisions, savings behaviour and human-capital accumulation (longer horizons encourage education and skill investments), thereby feeding into growth. These mechanisms are standard in endogenous growth and human-capital models. According to World Bank (2021), public spending only translates into growth if it improves human-capital outcomes. Studies emphasise that fiscal allocations without commensurate gains in literacy and life expectancy produce limited growth dividends – i.e., literacy rate and life expectancy are not merely controls but mediators of the spending → growth pathway. Empirical work for Nigeria shows that improvements in literacy and life expectancy are associated with higher labour productivity and positive long-run responses in RGDP when spending is converted into service delivery and learning/health gains. Recent analysis by Jibir, Bello and Amos (2024) point to low efficiency of public spending in Nigeria’s education and health sectors – inefficiencies, leakages, weak governance and poor targeting reduce the growth return to each naira spent. This explains why some studies find small or insignificant macro effects even when budget shares rise. Complementary investments (infrastructure, governance, teacher training, primary care, nutrition) and donor programs

that improve service delivery can raise the marginal productivity of public spending.

The Nigerian policy environment has seen renewed large-scale financing from multilateral partners to boost health and education (World Bank packages in 2024–2025), reflecting recognition that scaling quality human capital investments is central to growth and resilience. These financing flows make it especially timely to assess whether public investments (and the resulting changes in literacy and life expectancy) are delivering sustainable growth gains and where policy should shift – from increasing budget shares to improving composition and efficiency.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 The New Public Management (NPM) Theory

The New Public Management (NPM) emerged in the late 20th century as a reform paradigm designed to improve the efficiency, effectiveness, and accountability of public sector institutions. Rooted in public choice theory and managerialism, it emphasizes the application of private-sector principles in the public sector to enhance service delivery and optimize resource allocation (Hood, 1991; Pollitt and Bouckaert, 2017). Proponents such as Christopher Hood and Osborne and Gaebler (1992) argue that public organizations must be restructured to operate more efficiently, focusing on results rather than rigid processes. The core principles of NPM include decentralization of authority,

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performance measurement through output and outcome indicators, emphasis on efficiency and cost-effectiveness, competition through outsourcing and public–private partnerships, citizen orientation in service delivery, and accountability through performance-based management (Hood, 1991; Dunleavy et al., 2006; Christensen and Læg Reid, 2020). Unlike traditional bureaucratic models that stress rules and hierarchy, NPM calls for innovation, managerial flexibility, and service quality.

In the Nigerian context, the possible adaptation of NPM to economic growth lies in strengthening the efficiency of public expenditure management, particularly in critical sectors such as health and education that directly influence human capital development. By applying performance-based budgeting, ensuring transparency in fund allocation, and fostering competition through private-sector collaboration, Nigeria can improve service delivery outcomes that raise literacy rates, life expectancy, and ultimately economic performance (World Bank, 2023; Akinola and Tijani, 2022). However, the adaptation of NPM in Nigeria must consider local institutional realities—weak governance, corruption, and political interference often undermine reform initiatives. Scholars argue that while NPM principles can improve public financial management and policy implementation, they should be hybridized with governance and accountability frameworks tailored to the

Nigerian institutional environment (Adeyemo and Oladejo, 2021; Peters, 2018).

Thus, the NPM framework provides a theoretical basis for linking public sector reforms, efficient expenditure in education and health, and improved socioeconomic outcomes, which collectively contribute to sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

2.2.2 The Keynesian Multiplier

The Keynesian multiplier is a central concept in macroeconomic theory that explains how an initial change in autonomous spending—particularly government expenditure—can generate a magnified effect on aggregate output. The theoretical foundation was laid by John Maynard Keynes (1936) in his *General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money*, while Richard Kahn (1931) earlier formalized the employment multiplier in his work on public works spending. The essence of the multiplier is that government expenditure injects income into the economy, which induces further rounds of consumption and investment spending until leakages such as taxes, savings, and imports reduce the cycle. In its simplest form, the multiplier is expressed as $k = \frac{1}{(1 - MPC)}$, where

MPC denotes the marginal propensity to consume (Corporate Finance Institute, 2023).

The core principles of the Keynesian multiplier emphasize that fiscal policy has the capacity to stabilize and stimulate aggregate demand, especially during periods of underutilized

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capacity or economic downturns. The magnitude of the multiplier depends on the structure of the economy, including the marginal propensity to consume, the openness of the economy, and the level of idle resources. Studies confirm that multipliers are generally larger when public spending is directed toward productive investments such as education, health, and infrastructure, which enhance long-term supply capacity in addition to short-term demand stimulation (IMF, 2023; World Bank, 2023). By contrast, recurrent spending or expenditures with high import content tend to have smaller multiplier effects due to leakages. However, the application of the Keynesian multiplier in the Nigerian economy faces challenges that may weaken the fiscal multiplier effect. High import dependence causes substantial leakages, limiting the domestic demand effect of government spending. Likewise, issues of corruption, weak budget execution, and poor targeting of public expenditure reduce efficiency and erode the potential growth impact of fiscal interventions (Adeyemo & Oladejo, 2021). Empirical studies suggest that while Nigeria's fiscal multipliers are positive, they are often smaller than those in more diversified economies, underscoring the need for reforms in public financial management and the prioritization of productive, high-multiplier spending (CBN, 2024; IMF, 2023).

2.3 Empirical Review

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Obriki and Onuora (2024), investigated public sector investment and economic growth in Nigeria utilizing four explanatory variables as proxies for public sector investment indicators (education, transportation and communication, health and social and community services) while real gross domestic product was used as a proxy for economic growth in Nigeria. The ECM regression results revealed public investment in education and social and community services has a positive and a significant effect on economic growth while public in transportation and communication and health has an insignificant effect on economic growth. Based on these findings, it was recommended that government through their fiscal and monetary policy tools should ensure there is huge continuous public investment in the educational sector for improving the development of the economy.

Ugbaka and Ihuoma (2024) investigated the relationship between health outcomes and industrial productivity in Nigeria for the period 1990 through 2022 with the use of the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) methodology. The study found that in both long run and short run period, changes in mortality rate, morbidity rate, infant mortality, literacy rate and life expectancy significantly affect the level of industrial productivity in Nigeria.

Akujuobi, et. al (2023), analysed government expenditure and economic growth of Nigeria for the period 1981-2021. Government expenditure

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was proxied with expenditure on education, health, social and community services while government total investment and net foreign trade were included as the intervening variables. Economic growth was proxied with gross domestic product. The long run analysis revealed that government education expenditure had negative significant effect on Gross Domestic Product while health expenditure had positive significant effect on Gross Domestic Product. The study concluded that government expenditure has not been appropriately channelled towards the education sector and recommended that government should increase budget allocations to education sector and encourage private stake holders to invest in the education sector as well as engaging in foreign partnership in funding the health sector.

Ojo and Ojo (2022), looked at Nigeria's health expenditure, education, and economic growth, spanning from 1981 to 2019. Their paper used principal component analysis (PCA) to calculate variables. The study used an error correction model (ECM) as an estimating approach. According to the empirical data, government disbursement on education and health has a positive and considerable impact on economic growth and interaction.

Liu (2021) used Cobb-Douglas production function model to analyse the relationship between public education expenditure and China's economic growth and explores the

impact of the proportion of public education expenditure in primary, secondary and tertiary education expenditure on economic growth. The results show that public education expenditure has a positive effect on economic growth. The research results suggested that China should increase financial investment in education and optimize the expenditure structure of three-level education.

2.4 Research Gap

Despite extensive literature on government expenditure and growth in Nigeria, most studies have concentrated on aggregate spending without disaggregating into critical sectors like health and education, thereby overlooking their distinct contributions to long-run performance. Moreover, while public spending is often linked to growth, few studies explicitly incorporate literacy rate and life expectancy as outcome channels through which investment in human capital translates into higher productivity and GDP. Existing evidence is also largely short-term in focus and relies on limited econometric techniques, which neglect the long-run dynamics and endogeneity between expenditure and growth. Thus, there remains a gap in understanding how targeted public investment in education and health—mediated by literacy and life expectancy—affects Nigeria's long-run economic performance, which this study seeks to fill using robust time-series approaches.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

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The study adopts an ex-post facto research design, utilizing secondary time-series data for Nigeria covering the period 1986–2023. This design is appropriate because it allows for the systematic analysis of historical data to establish long-run relationships between public investment in human capital and economic growth.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the New Public Management (NPM) theory, which emphasizes efficiency, accountability, and performance-driven allocation of public resources. The theory is relevant because it advocates that government spending should be evaluated not only by the amount allocated but by the outcomes achieved, such as improved literacy and life expectancy. In this context, NPM provides the conceptual basis for linking public expenditure in education and health with measurable human capital outcomes and their subsequent effect on economic performance (RGDP) in Nigeria.

3.3 Sources of Data

Data will be obtained from reliable secondary sources including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, the World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI), and reports from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). Specifically, data on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), public expenditure on education, public expenditure on health, literacy rate, and life expectancy will be extracted for the study period.

3.4 Model Specification

The functional relationship is expressed as:

$$RGDP_t = f(PSIE_t, PSIH_t, LITR_t, LEXP_t) \quad (1)$$

Where:

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product (proxy for economic performance)

PSIE = Public sector investment in education

PSIH = Public sector investment in health

LITR = Literacy rate

LEXP = Life expectancy

The econometric form of the model is:

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PSIE_t + \beta_2 PSIH_t + \beta_3 LITR_t + \beta_4 LEXP_t \quad (2)$$

However, by taking the natural logarithm of RGDP, PSIE and PSIH to curtail the effects of spurious regression, we have:

$$LN RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LN PSIE_t + \beta_2 LN PSIH_t + \beta_3 LITR_t + \beta_4 LEXP_t \quad (3)$$

Where:

β_0 = Intercept of the model

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Long-run coefficients of the explanatory variables

ε_t = Error term

LN = Natural logarithm

3.5 Estimation Technique

The study employs the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) technique, developed by Phillips and Hansen (1990), which is suitable for estimating long-run relationships in cointegrated time-series data. FMOLS corrects

for serial correlation and endogeneity that may bias Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimates, making it appropriate for the present study. Prior to estimation, the following diagnostic procedures will be undertaken:

1. Unit root tests (Augmented Dickey-Fuller - ADF) to determine the stationarity properties of the variables. The ADF test regression equation with a constant is:

$$\Delta Y_T = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{T-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k a_j \Delta Y_{T-1} + \varepsilon_T \quad (4)$$

2. Johansen cointegration test to establish whether a long-run relationship exists among the variables.

3. Application of FMOLS to obtain efficient and consistent estimates of the long-run coefficients.

Thus, the general specification follows:

$$\text{Cointegration equation: } Y_t = \alpha + \beta X_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

Where: Y_t is the dependent variable, X_t is the independent variable(s), α is the intercept, β is the coefficient of X_t and ε_t is the error term.

However, the FMOLS estimator makes semi-parametric adjustments to the OLS estimator.

Thus:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + X_{it}'\beta + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (6)$$

Where: Y_{it} is the dependent variable for entity i at t time, α_i represents individual-specific fixed effects (if included in the model), X_{it}' is a vector of independent variables for entity i at t time, β is the vector of long-run coefficients to be estimated (this is the primary focus of the FMOLS estimation), and ε_{it} is the error term.

3.6 Justification of Method

FMOLS is selected over other methods such as OLS or ARDL because it provides robust estimates in small samples, corrects for possible endogeneity, and is well-suited for long-run policy-oriented research. This aligns with the NPM theory's emphasis on outcome-oriented evaluation of public investment, enabling the study to establish reliable evidence on how health and education spending, as well as literacy and life expectancy, contribute to Nigeria's long-term economic performance.

3.7 Test of Significance

The significance was tested at 5% level of significance using the coefficients of the independent variables and following the Rule: Reject the Null hypothesis if the t-prob is less than 0.05, otherwise accept the Null hypothesis when t-prob is greater than 0.05, i.e. Reject if t-prob < 0.05, Accept if t-prob > 0.05

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1: Data for Public Sector Investment in Education, Public Sector Investment in Health, Literacy Rate, Life Expectancy and RGDP in Nigeria (1986-2023)

YEAR	RGDP (N'B)	PSIE (N'B)	PSIH (N'B)	LEXP (YRS)	LITR (%)
1986	9.7515329	-1.3470736	0.91629	45.98	54
1987	9.7830328	-1.469676	0.95935	46.02	54
1988	9.8538083	0.3784364	1.16627	46.07	54
1989	9.8728203	1.1019401	1.27257	46.18	54
1990	9.9841549	0.8754687	1.37372	46.04	55
1991	9.987732	0.2311117	1.54756	45.69	55
1992	10.033004	-1.2378744	2.49651	45.67	55
1993	10.012442	2.1838016	2.87187	45.79	55
1994	9.9941265	1.9987736	3.01896	45.51	55
1995	9.9933995	2.2772673	3.16336	45.49	55
1996	10.034502	2.442347	3.19294	45.57	55
1997	10.06345	2.6979999	3.41313	45.79	55
1998	10.088935	2.6093342	3.767	46.04	55
1999	10.09476	3.7752865	3.90439	46.61	55
2000	10.143702	4.0596952	4.58619	47.19	60
2001	10.201194	3.6859402	4.81357	47.62	60
2002	10.343814	4.3886407	4.86823	47.93	60
2003	10.414712	4.1710302	4.96187	48.44	60
2004	10.503186	4.3372907	5.07311	48.77	60
2005	10.565583	4.4164281	5.20186	49.3	60
2006	10.624412	4.7792745	5.33074	49.73	70
2007	10.688242	5.015817	5.44553	50.03	70
2008	10.753697	5.099729	5.57674	50.22	70
2009	10.831	4.9208273	5.68389	50.71	70
2010	10.923586	5.1404933	5.802	50.94	70

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2011	10.971303	5.8165157	5.95892	51.36	70
2012	11.013205	5.8533512	6.09343	51.5	70
2013	11.065745	5.9671719	6.2514	51.71	70
2014	11.126931	5.8399292	6.42167	51.79	70
2015	11.153113	5.7844096	6.52606	51.84	70
2016	11.136812	5.8268329	6.61416	52.04	58
2017	11.144838	6.0013086	6.66543	52.3	58
2018	11.163883	6.1426821	6.71136	52.55	58
2019	11.185727	6.3854087	6.79815	52.91	58
2020	11.167622	6.4720256	6.85787	52.89	58
2021	11.203444	6.4306715	6.94978	52.68	63
2022	11.221937	6.5553266	7.08356	55.12	63
2023	11.263645	6.6240338	7.1346	54.46	63

Sources: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, the World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI), and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)

4.1.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics summarize and describe the main features of a dataset, such as its central

tendency, dispersion, and shape, using measures like mean, median, standard deviation, and range. They provide a concise overview of data patterns without making inferences about a larger population.

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Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics for Public Sector Investment in Education, Public Sector Investment in Health, Literacy Rate, Life Expectancy and RGDP in Nigeria (1986-2023)

	LNRGDP	LNPSIE	LNPSIH	LITR	LEXP
Mean	10.53576	3.84821	4.644053	60.65789	49.11789
Median	10.53438	4.402534	5.137485	59	49.035
Maximum	11.26364	6.624034	7.134596	70	55.12
Minimum	9.751533	-1.46968	0.916291	54	45.49
Std. Dev.	0.523314	2.397781	1.987758	6.204951	2.9941
Skewness	0.029333	-0.81066	-0.56391	0.585238	0.222721
Kurtosis	1.392125	2.589313	2.042242	1.771729	1.671958
Jarque-Bera	4.098782	4.429114	3.466325	4.557885	3.106679
Probability	0.128813	0.109202	0.176725	0.102392	0.21154
Sum	400.359	146.232	176.474	2305	1866.48
Sum Sq. Dev.	10.13274	212.7261	146.1937	1424.553	331.6914
Observations	38	38	38	38	38

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The descriptive statistics in Table 4.2 reveal that economic growth (LNRGDP) is stable with minimal variation, while public sector investments in education (LNPSIE) and health (LNPSIH) show high volatility and occasional underfunding, as indicated by negative skewness and wide value ranges. Literacy rate (LITR) and life expectancy (LEXP) display moderate consistency with relatively low dispersion. All variables are approximately normally distributed (Jarque-Bera $p > 0.05$) but

exhibit platykurtic characteristics, suggesting flatter-than-normal distributions. Overall, the dataset is suitable for further econometric analysis, though fluctuations in social sector investments highlight potential structural imbalances.

4.1.3 Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis was carried out to examine the degree of association between the variables used in the study. The results of the correlation matrix are presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix of Public Sector Investment in Education, Public Sector Investment in Health, Literacy Rate, Life Expectancy and RGDP in Nigeria (1986-2023)

	LNRGDP	LNPSIE	LNPSIH	LITR	LEXP
LNRGDP	1	0.912047	0.946257	0.67076	0.977153
LNPSIE	0.912047	1	0.969093	0.657403	0.876368
LNPSIH	0.946257	0.969093	1	0.660402	0.909645
LITR	0.67076	0.657403	0.660402	1	0.633191
LEXP	0.977153	0.876368	0.909645	0.633191	1

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The correlation results indicate that real gross domestic product (LNRGDP) is strongly and positively correlated with public sector investment in education (LNPSIE) and health (LNPSIH), with correlation coefficients of 0.91 and 0.95, respectively. This suggests that increases in public expenditure on education and health are closely associated with improvements in economic growth. LNRGDP also exhibits a very strong positive correlation with life expectancy (LEXP) at 0.98, implying that economic growth and human development outcomes are closely intertwined in Nigeria. Public sector investments in education (LNPSIE) and health (LNPSIH) are also highly correlated (0.97), reflecting the government’s tendency to allocate resources to both sectors simultaneously as part of its human capital development strategy. Both education and health expenditures are positively associated with life expectancy, with coefficients of 0.88 and 0.91, respectively, indicating that higher social sector investment contributes positively to improved welfare outcomes. The literacy rate

(LITR) shows a moderate but positive relationship with the other variables, recording correlation coefficients of 0.67 with LNRGDP, 0.66 with LNPSIH, and 0.63 with LEXP. These results suggest that while literacy plays an important role in supporting growth and human development, its effect is not as strong as that of direct sectoral investments in education and health. Overall, the correlation analysis reveals strong interrelationships among the variables, particularly between economic growth, life expectancy, and public sector investment in education and health. This supports the theoretical expectation that human capital development and welfare outcomes are critical determinants of long-term economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Unit Root Test

Prior to the estimation of the regression model, it is important to determine the stationarity properties of the variables in order to avoid spurious regression results. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was employed to examine the time-series characteristics of the

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variables. The results of the unit root test are presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Summary of the Unit Root Test Result @ 5% Critical Value

VARIABLE S	LEVEL		FIRST DIFFERENCE		ORDER OF INTEGRATION
	ADF TEST STAT.	CRITICAL VAL. @ 5%	ADF TEST STAT.	CRITICAL VAL. @ 5%	
LNGRGDP	-0.641667 (0.8486)	-2.945842	-3.930270 (0.0046)	-2.945842	I(1)
LNPSIE	-2.084229 (0.0729)	-2.967767	-2.204853 (0.0289)	-1.953858	I(1)
LNPSIH	-0.428743 (0.5195)	-1.952910	-2.329273 (0.0215)	-1.952910	I(1)
LITR	-1.580357 (0.4824)	-2.943427	-5.916080 (0.0000)	-1.950394	I(1)
LEXP	1.418626 (0.9987)	-2.945842	-7.197674 (0.0000)	-2.945842	I(1)

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The results reveal that all the variables - real gross domestic product (LNGRGDP), public sector investment in education (LNPSIE), public sector investment in health (LNPSIH), literacy rate (LITR), and life expectancy (LEXP) - are non-stationary at their levels, as their ADF test statistics are less than the critical values at the 5 percent significance level, with high p-values. However, at first difference, all the series become stationary, as their ADF test statistics are more negative than the corresponding 5 percent critical values and their p-values are significant at 0.05. Thus, the variables are integrated of order one, I(1). This finding justifies the use of econometric techniques such

as the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), or Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), which are suitable for handling variables that are stationary at first difference. However, we shall first test for a long-run relationship in the model. Thus, the Johansen cointegration test becomes most appropriate in estimating the long-run relationship among the variables.

4.2.2 Johansen Cointegration Test

Having established that all the variables are integrated of order one, I(1), the Johansen cointegration test was employed to determine whether a long-run equilibrium relationship exists among the variables of interest. Both the trace statistic and the maximum eigenvalue

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statistic were used, and the results are presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Johansen Cointegration Test Results

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.** Critical Value	Max- Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.** Critical Value
None *	0.669190	105.3606	69.81889	0.0000	39.82360	33.87687	0.0087
At most 1 *	0.631822	65.53695	47.85613	0.0005	35.97075	27.58434	0.0033
At most 2	0.464041	29.56620	29.79707	0.0532	22.45312	21.13162	0.0324
At most 3	0.140470	7.113080	15.49471	0.5645	5.449303	14.26460	0.6844
At most 4	0.045164	1.663777	3.841465	0.1971	1.663777	3.841465	0.1971

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The results from the trace statistic indicate the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration ($r = 0$) and at most one cointegrating equation ($r \leq 1$), since the trace statistics (105.36 and 65.54) are greater than their critical values (69.82 and 47.86) at the 5 percent level of significance. Similarly, the maximum eigenvalue test confirms the existence of three cointegrating vectors, with the statistics (39.82, 35.97 and 22.45) exceeding their respective critical values (33.88, 27.58 and 21.13). Therefore, both the trace and max-eigen statistics consistently suggest the existence of at least two and three cointegrating relationships among the variables respectively. This implies

that real GDP, public sector investment in education, public sector investment in health, literacy rate, and life expectancy move together in the long run, establishing a stable long-run equilibrium relationship despite short-run fluctuations.

4.3 Estimation of the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS)

To estimate the long-run relationship among the variables after establishing cointegration, the study employed the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method, which corrects for endogeneity and serial correlation in the regressors. The results are presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: FMOLS Long-run Estimation Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNPSIE	-0.012414	0.026285	-0.472271	0.6399
LNPSIH	0.090614	0.035502	2.552344	0.0157
LITR	0.005930	0.003250	1.824979	0.0774
LEXP	0.121256	0.012593	9.628675	0.0000
C	3.853535	0.548423	7.026568	0.0000

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The results of the FMOLS in Table 4.6 show that public sector investment in education (LNPSIE) has a negative but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth (LNREGDP), with a coefficient of -0.012 and a probability value of 0.640. This suggests that fluctuations in education spending did not translate directly into long-term growth during the period under review, possibly due to issues of misallocation, inefficiency, or lagged effects of educational investment.

Public sector investment in health (LNPSIH) has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth, with a coefficient of 0.091 and a probability value of 0.016. This indicates that a 1 percent increase in health investment leads to approximately a 0.09 percent increase in real GDP, underscoring the critical role of healthcare in enhancing human capital productivity.

The literacy rate (LITR) has a positive effect (0.006) on economic growth but weakly

significant at the 5 percent level ($p = 0.077$). This suggests that improvements in literacy contribute positively to growth, though the effect is relatively small, reflecting persistent challenges in educational quality and access.

Life expectancy (LEXP) exerts the strongest and most significant positive influence on economic growth, with a coefficient of 0.121 and a probability value of 0.000. This implies that a 1 percent increase in life expectancy is associated with about a 0.12 percent increase in real GDP. The result highlights the importance of population health and longevity in sustaining economic performance.

The constant term (C) is positive and significant, reflecting baseline growth dynamics not captured by the explanatory variables.

The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.969 indicates that about 97 percent of the variation in real GDP is explained by the model, confirming a strong goodness of fit.

The post-estimation tests – Normality test, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity test,

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Ramsey RESET test and the CUSUM graph – affirm the robustness of the model.

In summary, the FMOLS results establish that while education spending does not have a direct and immediate effect on economic growth, health expenditure, literacy, and life expectancy significantly enhance growth performance in Nigeria. This finding reinforces the argument that human capital development, especially through health and welfare improvements, plays a pivotal role in driving long-term economic growth.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide significant insights into the relationship between human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria, using real GDP as the dependent variable and public investment in education, public investment in health, literacy rate, and life expectancy as explanatory variables.

The result for public investment in education (LNPSIE) revealed a negative but statistically insignificant impact on economic growth. This outcome contrasts with the theoretical expectations of endogenous growth theory, which emphasizes education as a driver of productivity and long-run growth (Romer, 1990). However, the result is consistent with empirical studies such as Dauda (2010) and Ogujiuba and Adeniyi (2021), which found that education spending in Nigeria often fails to translate into economic growth due to issues of mismanagement, corruption, and weak

institutional capacity. This finding suggests that while government expenditure on education has increased over the years, inefficiencies in allocation and the long gestation period of educational investments may explain its insignificant impact in the short to medium term.

In contrast, public investment in health (LNPSIH) showed a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth. This aligns with the human capital theory advanced by Schultz (1961) and Becker (1964), which posits that health improvements enhance labour productivity and, by extension, economic performance. The result also supports studies by Bloom and Canning (2008) and Enoma and Mustafa (2020), which emphasize the strong link between healthcare investment and economic growth in developing economies. For Nigeria, the finding underscores the importance of health sector financing in improving labour efficiency and reducing the economic burden of disease.

Literacy rate (LITR) had a positive but weakly significant impact on growth. This suggests that while literacy contributes to economic performance, its effect in Nigeria remains modest. This outcome could be attributed to disparities in educational access, regional inequalities, and the persistent challenge of poor educational quality, which limit the effectiveness of literacy in enhancing productivity. Similar findings were reported by

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Okafor et al. (2010), who noted that improvements in literacy in Nigeria have not been matched with adequate job creation and skill utilization.

Life expectancy (LEXP) emerged as the most influential determinant of economic growth, with a strong positive and highly significant effect. This result is consistent with the health-led growth hypothesis, which argues that healthier populations live longer, remain more productive, and accumulate more human capital over their lifetimes. The finding corroborates evidence from Bloom, Kuhn, and Prettner (2020), who highlighted the role of increased longevity in sustaining growth in developing countries. For Nigeria, the implication is that policies targeting health improvements and reductions in mortality could substantially enhance long-term growth outcomes.

Overall, the discussion of findings suggests that while Nigeria's investments in human capital have yielded some positive outcomes, particularly in health and life expectancy, the benefits of education spending remain elusive due to systemic inefficiencies. The results affirm the view that the quality, efficiency, and effective implementation of human capital policies are as important as the volume of spending in achieving sustainable economic growth.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

This study examined the long-run impact of public sector investment in education and health on Nigeria's economic performance between 1986 and 2023, with real GDP (LNRGDP) as the dependent variable, while public investment in education (LNPSIE), public investment in health (LNPSIH), literacy rate (LITR), and life expectancy (LEXP) served as the explanatory variables. The analysis employed the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) estimation technique after confirming stationarity of the variables at first difference and the presence of cointegration among the variables. Data for the study were culled from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, the World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI), and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The descriptive statistics revealed that all variables were normally distributed, with life expectancy and literacy rate showing relative stability compared to public investment measures. The correlation results indicated strong positive associations between human capital variables and economic growth, especially life expectancy and health investment. The unit root and Johansen cointegration tests confirmed long-run relationships among the variables. The FMOLS results showed that public investment

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in education exerted a negative and statistically insignificant impact on economic growth, suggesting inefficiencies in the Nigerian education system. Conversely, public investment in health had a positive and significant effect on growth, while literacy rate displayed a positive but weakly significant effect. Life expectancy emerged as the most influential factor, exhibiting a strong and highly significant positive impact on economic growth.

5.3 Conclusion

This study concludes that human capital development significantly influences Nigeria's economic growth, with health investment and life expectancy showing the strongest effects, while education spending remains undermined by inefficiencies and weak implementation. Although literacy contributes modestly, its impact is constrained by poor quality and regional disparities. Overall, the findings highlight that Nigeria's growth potential depends not only on the volume of investment in education and health but also on the efficiency, quality, and governance of such investments to ensure they yield sustainable economic outcomes.

5.3 Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. Reform Education Spending: Government should prioritize efficient allocation of educational funds, ensuring that investments

target infrastructure, teacher training, and research. Measures to curb corruption and waste in the education sector should be strengthened.

2. Scale up Health Investments: Increased funding for healthcare should focus on primary healthcare delivery, access to essential medicines, and health infrastructure, particularly in rural areas. Such investments would improve labour productivity and reduce economic losses from poor health.

3. Promote Literacy and Skills Development: Literacy policies should be complemented with vocational and technical training programs to address the mismatch between education and labour market demands. Regional literacy disparities should also be reduced through targeted interventions.

4. Enhance Life Expectancy through Health and Social Policies: Government should implement policies that improve nutrition, maternal and child health, and preventive healthcare. Efforts to address insecurity and poverty, which indirectly affect life expectancy, should also be intensified.

5. Strengthen Institutions and Policy Implementation: Transparent governance structures are needed to ensure that human capital investments yield tangible results. Monitoring and evaluation frameworks should be built into education and health programs to enhance accountability.

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